

Distribution of Seafood Production in Bajo Sector of Gorontalo Province Indonesia

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Abstract:- The research was conducted in Bajo Tilamuta Village, Boalemo District, Gorontalo Province. Marketing is one of the most important activities in marketing seafood in Bajo Village in Boalemo, because one of the factors that becomes a constraint is the availability of adequate infrastructure. In Bajo Lemito Village, Boalemo Regency has high potential for fishery such as; Cucumbers and Pearls of the Sea, Mabe, Japing. The purpose of this study is to study the economic situation in Bajo Tilamuta Village Boalemo District, living conditions of fishermen, production and marketing. The research method used is descriptive by using purposive sampling method that is direct sampling because it is known before the sample can represent population. While the data analysis using quantitative and qualitative methods. The qualitative method is to provide a discussion of quantitative data relating to the theoretical aspects and separated by categories to get conclusions. The results of this study provide information that the sea cucumber classified as having a good marketing efficiency and categorized into the marketing that has been efficient when marketing pearl shells, Mabe, marketing Japing not efficient.

Keywords:- Marketing Efficiency, Sea Cucumber Cucumber, shell mabe, japing shell.

I. PRELIMINARY

Fishery Development is a part of national development where the main target of development in the field of fishery sub-sector economy implemented by the Indonesian people themselves, whether the business of producing, processing, and marketing. To achieve these fisheries development objectives, various policies adopted by the government, as set out in the Guidelines of State Policy (GBHN) in the five-year development plan, namely the fourth lamp can be seen fisheries development policies that have been outlined by the government aimed at improving production and business productivity as well as providing business opportunities in productive employment. In addition to improving facilities

$MP = Pr - Pf$

MP=Margin Marketing

Pr: prices at the retailer level

Pf: price at the fisherman level.

and infrastructure to achieve increased income of fishermen and fish farmers, expanded work in the field of fishery sub sector to reduce damage to resources and foreign exchange resources from non-oil commodities. Although many policies have been established to achieve the aims of fisheries development, but the reality has not been able to meet the desired expectations. Increased production and productivity of fishermen and fish farmers programmed has not provided satisfactory results. In general, the income level of fishermen is still relatively low. Marketing is one of the most important activities to help increase the income of fishermen. Marketing is one of the most important activities to improve the economy, especially in the field of fisheries. In marketing seafood, it is necessary to provide facilities and infrastructure such as fishing port, fish market and others. The Bajo fishermen in Boalemo Regency produce seafood such as: sea cucumber, mother shell, Mabe shell and Japing shell. Mubyarto (1985) states, Marketing or distribution is a kind of economic activity that serves to bring or deliver goods from producers to consumers. Hippy (1992), that the types of marine products in the village of Bajo Boalemo are fish such as tude, skipjack, mullet, sea cucumber and shellfish. As far as observation to date, no research has been done to disclose data and information on the efficiency of Bajo fishery product seafarers, hence the writer feel the need to do research to know more about it.

II. METHODS

The method used is the sampling or sampling method, because it has been done pre-survey before, then the village sampled is the village of Bajo Tilamuta Boalemo district where most of the population is Bajo tribe. Sampling is done purposively, choosing the sample directly because it is known before that the selected sample can represent it. While the data analysis using the trade margin as a measuring tool which is the average price of producers divide the market selling price. According Sutarno (2014), mathematically the number of marketing margins can be calculated based on the formula

For efficiency can be seen from the percentage of income received by Farmer's share (Fs). The farmers section

$$LP = He - M \times 100\%$$

He:

LP: Prices received by fishermen
 M: Total Margin (Rp/kg)
 He: Retail price at the production level
 HK: Price on Consumer

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Average price / kg of this type of seafood can be seen in the table below:
 Table 1. Average Prices at Fisherman's level, Wholesaler Traders and wholesalers

No	type of seafood	Average Price Fishermen	Price Per/Kg Collecting Merchants	Wholesalers Collectors
1	Sea Cucumber	140000	170000	190000
2	Shellfish Pearl	26000	29000	34000
3	ShellfishMabe	18000	22000	27000
4	ShellfishJaping	14000	18000	24000

To see the marketing efficiency of authors using *Farmer Share (FS)* can be seen from the following calculation:

1. The average price of Sea Cucumber is: $190000 - 140000 = 50,000$
 Margin : 50,000

$$\text{Farmer Share} = \frac{140000 - 50000}{140000} \times 100\% = 64\%$$

2. The average price of pearl shells is: $34000 - 26000 = 8000$
 Margin : 8000

$$\text{Farmer share} = \frac{26000 - 8000}{26000} \times 100\% = 69\%$$

3. The average price of Mabe's shell is: $27000 - 18000 = 9000$
 Margin : 9000

$$\text{Farmer share} = \frac{18000 - 9000}{18000} \times 100\% = 50\%$$

4. Average price of Japing shell is: $24000 - 14000 = 10000$
 Margin: 10000

$$\text{Farmer share} = \frac{14000 - 10000}{14000} \times 100\% = 28\%$$

From table 1 above can be seen that the margin obtained by wholesalers and has a large margin than Fishermen and merchant collectors.

While the margins of the fishermen to collecting traders have a smaller difference than the wholesalers. To see the marketing efficiency of marine products can be seen in the table below:

Table 2. Efficiency of Marine Product Marketing in Bajo Tilamuta Village Boalemo Regency

No	Name of Seafood	Results Percentage (%) Marketing Efficiency
1	Sea Cucumber	64 Efficient
2	Pearl Shellfish	69 Efficient
3	Mabe Shellfish	50 Efficient
4	Japing Shellfish	28 NotEfficient

Cucumbers, Mother shells, Mabe shells have efficient marketing because the percentage of income received at the producer level is > 50%. Margin marketing is done to know the marketing efficiency of a product from producer level to consumer level. Margin marketing is the price difference that occurs with the amount of profit in each marketing agency involved in marketing activities. There are different cost components of each marketing channel pattern, thus impacting marketing margins on existing marketing institutions in Bajo Tilamuta village, Boalemo district.

IV. CONCLUSION

1. The most efficient marketing channel of Bajo fishery products in Boalemo is Sea Cucumber, Shellfish Pearl, Shellfish Mabe
2. The highest share of farmers in the marketing channels of Shellfish Pearl.

Recognition

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